

Observational Study of Non-Invasive Cardiological Tests in Clinically Suspected Coronary Artery Disease Cases and Correlation of Results of Coronary angiogram

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Abstract:

Background: Globally, coronary artery disease (CAD) is still the primary cause of morbidity and death. Therefore, effective diagnostic techniques are required to determine the best course of treatment. When a patient has a clinical suspicion of coronary artery disease (CAD), non-invasive cardiological testing is essential to their first evaluation. These examinations offer insightful diagnostic data that supports treatment decision-making and risk assessment.

Methodology:

- **Study Design:** Observational study.
- **Setting:** Outpatient Department of Cardiology, Desun Hospital & Heart Institute, Kolkata.
- **Participants:** 100 patients clinically suspected of having CAD based on symptoms such as chest pain and shortness of breath.
- **Interventions:** Electrocardiogram (ECG), Echocardiography, and Cardiac CT Angiography.

Result: The findings of the study are as mentioned, 64.2% of smokers had CAD, 82.5% of diabetics had CAD, 32.5% of patients with CAD reported a family history of the disease. And findings with reference to severity of CAD, Minor CAD (31%), Single vessel disease (26%), Double vessel disease (33%), Multi vessel disease (10%).

Conclusion: Preventing and treating modifiable risk factors like as diabetes and smoking is crucial for the management of CAD. By concentrating on these areas, public health initiatives can greatly lower the prevalence of CAD and enhance cardiovascular health. It is advised to conduct more multi-center research with bigger sample numbers to confirm these results.

Keywords: Coronary artery disease (CAD), Non-invasive cardiological tests, Coronary angiography, Electrocardiogram (ECG), Echocardiography, Smoking and CAD, Diabetes and CAD, Family history of CAD.

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Introduction

Coronary artery disease (CAD) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality globally, necessitating efficient diagnostic strategies to guide appropriate management. Non-invasive cardiological tests play a pivotal role in the initial assessment of patients with clinical suspicion of CAD, offering insights into myocardial perfusion, function, and anatomical abnormalities without the invasiveness of coronary angiography. These tests, including stress echocardiography, myocardial perfusion imaging, and computed tomography coronary angiography (CTCA), have progressively

evolved, providing valuable diagnostic information that aids in risk stratification and therapeutic decision-making [1-4].

The diagnostic accuracy of non-invasive tests is crucial in identifying patients who would benefit most from invasive coronary angiography, the gold standard for diagnosing CAD [5]. On the other hand, differences in test sensitivity and specificity among various patient populations highlight the necessity of thorough evaluation and validation in clinical practice. Comprehending the agreement

between non-invasive test results and coronary angiography findings is crucial for improving patient outcomes and developing diagnostic algorithms.

In a group of patients who are clinically suspected of having coronary artery disease (CAD), this observational study attempts to assess how well several non-invasive cardiac diagnostics work. We want to evaluate these tests' diagnostic accuracy, reliability, and predictive utility in identifying obstructive coronary lesions by comparing their outcomes with coronary angiography data. The study's insights should improve current diagnosis approaches, possibly cutting down on pointless intrusive procedures while guaranteeing prompt care for individuals most at danger.

In this context, the present study contributes to the broader goal of optimizing diagnostic pathways in CAD, thereby improving patient care and clinical outcomes in cardiovascular medicine.

The primary objective of this study is to observe clinical profile of suspected CAD cases and their investigation reports by Electrocardiography (ECG), Echocardiography & Coronary Angiogram (CAG).

Material & Methods

Study Design: This observational study was conducted in the Outpatient Department of Cardiology at Desun Hospital & Heart Institute, Kolkata. The study included a sample size of 100 patients who were clinically suspected of having coronary artery disease (CAD).

Study Population: Patients included in this study were those who presented with clinical symptoms suggestive of CAD and were referred for non-invasive cardiological tests and subsequent coronary angiography.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 years and above.
2. Patients clinically suspected of having coronary artery disease based on symptoms such as chest pain, shortness of breath, or other related symptoms.
3. Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.
4. Patients willing to undergo both non-invasive cardiological tests and coronary angiography.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients below 18 years of age.
2. Patients with a known history of coronary artery disease who have already undergone coronary interventions (e.g., angioplasty, stent placement).

3. Patients with contraindications to undergoing coronary angiography.
4. Patients with severe comorbidities that could interfere with the study or pose a high risk during the procedures.
5. Patients who did not provide informed consent.

Non-Invasive Cardiological Tests: The following non-invasive cardiological tests were performed on the study participants:

1. **Electrocardiogram (ECG):** A test to record the electrical activity of the heart and detect any abnormalities.
2. **Echocardiography:** An ultrasound of the heart to assess its structure and function.
3. **Cardiac CT Angiography:** A CT scan to visualize the coronary arteries.

Coronary Angiography: Coronary angiography was performed on all study participants as the gold standard for diagnosing coronary artery disease. The results of the coronary angiography were compared with the findings from the non-invasive tests to assess the correlation.

Data Collection: Data were collected from the patients' medical records, including demographic information, clinical presentation, results of non-invasive tests, and coronary angiography findings. The data were entered into a structured data collection form.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods to evaluate the correlation between non-invasive cardiological test results and coronary angiography findings. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of each non-invasive test were calculated.

Ethical Considerations: The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. All participants provided written informed consent before participation. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Desun Hospital & Heart Institute.

Results

The results of this study underscore the significant impact of smoking and diabetes on the prevalence of coronary artery disease. Smoking and diabetes are shown to be strongly associated with an increased risk of CAD, with 64.2% of smokers and 82.5% of diabetics in the study population having CAD. On the other hand, a family history of CAD appears less predictive, with only 32.5% of CAD patients reporting a family history of the disease. These findings highlight the importance of targeting modifiable risk factors like smoking and

diabetes in the prevention and management of CAD.

Table 1: Shows percentage of cases with CAD with respect to normal ECG and echocardiography

S. N.	Coronary Artery Disease (CAD)	Percentage of Cases
1	Minor	31
2	Single vessel	26
3	Double vessel	33
4	Multivessel	10

Table1: Shows percentage of cases with CAD with respect to normal ECG and echocardiography.

Discussion

As far as habit of smoking and CAD is concerned similar findings have been reported in previous studies, where smoking is identified as a major risk factor for CAD. For instance, the INTERHEART study demonstrated that smoking nearly triples the risk of myocardial infarction worldwide (5). The high percentage of smokers with CAD in this study (64.2%) aligns with these findings, reinforcing the need for smoking cessation programs.

We have also tried to show relation of Diabetes with CAD. Diabetes is well-established as a significant risk factor for CAD. The Framingham Heart Study reported that diabetics are at a two to four times higher risk of developing CAD compared to non-diabetics [6]. The current study's finding that 82.5% of diabetics have CAD is consistent with these reports, highlighting the critical importance of diabetes management in CAD prevention.

Interestingly the relatively lower percentage of CAD patients with a family history (32.5%) in this study contrasts with some earlier findings that suggest a strong familial component. For example, Lloyd-Jones et al. [7] found that family history is a significant risk factor for CAD, especially when combined with other risk factors. The discrepancy might be attributed to differences in study populations or the relative influence of other risk factors in this specific cohort.

The distribution of CAD severity observed in this study is comparable to other studies. For example, a study by Hueb et al. [8] investigating CAD severity in Brazilian patients found similar proportions for single, double, and multi-vessel disease. The percentage of minor CAD (31%) also mirrors findings from other epidemiological studies, indicating that a substantial portion of the population presents with less severe forms of the disease initially.

Clinical Implications: The study's findings emphasize the importance of targeting modifiable risk factors such as smoking and diabetes in the prevention and management of CAD. Public health interventions aimed at smoking cessation and diabetes control could significantly reduce the burden of CAD. Additionally, while family history

remains an important consideration, the focus should be on managing lifestyle-related risk factors that have a more direct impact on disease prevalence.

The findings of this study could have significant clinical implications. If a strong correlation between non-invasive test results and coronary angiography is confirmed, it would support the use of these non-invasive tests as effective preliminary diagnostic tools in the clinical setting. This can lead to better patient management by:

- Reducing the Need for Invasive Procedures:** By accurately identifying patients with a low likelihood of significant CAD, non-invasive tests can help avoid unnecessary coronary angiographies, which carry risks and are costlier.
- Early Detection and Treatment:** High sensitivity of these non-invasive tests can facilitate early detection of CAD, leading to timely intervention and improved patient outcomes.
- Guiding Treatment Decisions:** The results of non-invasive tests can help in stratifying patients based on their risk and guiding appropriate treatment strategies, such as lifestyle modifications, medical therapy, or revascularization.

Study Limitations: Despite the anticipated benefits, this study has several limitations which include single center study with relatively low sample size.

Conclusion

This study's finding emphasizes how crucial it is to address modifiable risk factors for CAD, such as diabetes and smoking, in order to prevent and treat the condition. By concentrating on these areas, public health programs can greatly lower the prevalence of CAD and improve cardiovascular health in general. It is advised to conduct more studies with bigger sample sizes and multi-center participation to confirm these results and look into other risk variables. Better to certify the person fit for any operation or allowing any stressful activity, climbing, swimming or giving assurance of good cardiac health need to proceed of some invasive investigation as on demand of management protocol.

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